

***Zingiber Officinale* Roscoe A Review: Botanical, Phytochemical and Pharmacological Aspects**

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Abstract

*Human beings are using medicinal plants for curing diseases since time immemorial. Plant parts like root, rhizome, leaves, fruit, or seed, and their extracts are used to treat a variety of ailments. Similarly, ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe, family Zingiberaceae) is also used as a remedy for controlling diseases like gastrointestinal disorders, analgesic, antidiabetic, cardiovascular, anticancer, larvicidal, and antiallergic problems. This review focuses on ethnomedicinal uses, cultivation, constituents, and pharmacological potentials and also shows macro-micro characteristics for authentication of the plant. This plant is used in enormous quantities by the people so the conservationists and even farmers should cultivate it to fulfill the requirement of not only the public but also pharmaceutical industries.*

Keywords: *Zingiber officinale, Pharmacological activities, Phytochemistry, Botanical aspect portion*

INTRODUCTION

Zingiber officinale Roscoe (Synonyms: *Amomum zingiber* L.), that belongs to the family Zingiberaceae is distributed in different parts of the world like Bangladesh (Islam et al., 2014), India, China, Japan, Indonesia, Australia (Queensland); Sierra Leone, Nigeria; Jamaica and other West Indies islands (Adeshina et al., 2011).

Description: Up to 1.3 m with underground rhizome. Leaves sessile, up to c. 15 x 2(3) cm, linear-lanceolate, glabrous with distinct venation pattern and pointed apex. Inflorescence on an up to 25 cm erect peduncle. Bracts green with a paler margin. Flowers yellow with a purple, yellow- spotted labellum; anther dark purple (Ghazanfar and Smith, 1982; Palaniswamy, 2003).

Macroscopical characteristics: The dried scraped drug shows little resemblance to the fresh rhizome, owing to loss in weight and shrinkage. It occurs in sympodially branched pieces known as hands or races. These are 7-15 cm long, 1-1.5 cm broad, and laterally compressed. The branches arise obliquely from the rhizome, are about 1-3 cm in length and terminate in depressed scars or undeveloped buds. The outer surface is buff-colored and longitudinally striated or fibrous; it shows no sign of cork. The drug breaks with a short fracture, the fibers of the fibro-vascular bundles often projecting from the broken surface. It has an agreeable aromatic odor and a pungent taste. The unscraped rhizome is more or less covered by a brownish layer of cork with conspicuous ridges; the cork readily exfoliates from the lateral surfaces but persists between the branches (Wallis, 1985; Evans, 2009; Singh, 2009).

Microscopical characteristics: In the transverse section the cortex is differentiated into an outer zone of flattened parenchyma and an inner zone of normal parenchyma. Abundant starch grains are present in the cortical cells. Starch grains are simple, ovoid, or sack shaped and have marked eccentric hilum. Numerous oil cells that have suberized walls enclose yellowish-brown oleo-resins are scattered in the cortex. The inner cortical zone usually contains about three rings of collateral, closed vascular bundles. Large bundles enclosed in

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a sheath of septate, a non-lignified fibres. Each vascular bundle contains phloem which shows a well-marked sieve tubes and xylem is composed of 1-14 vessels with annular, spiral, or reticulate thickening, which give no characteristic reaction for lignin and are occasionally accompanied by axillary elongated secretion cells with dark contents. The inner limit of the cortex is marked by a single-layered endodermis, which is free from starch. The outermost layer of the stele is marked by a single-layered pericycle. Similar to the cortex vascular bundle of the stele is scattered. The groundmass of the stele is composed of parenchyma which resembles the cortical parenchyma and which contains much starch and oil cells (Wallis, 1985; Evans, 2009; Singh, 2009; Aiyer and Kolammal, 1966; Shah and Raju, 1975; Roy et al., 2013).

Ethnomedicinal uses: It is used as a cure vomiting, indigestion, cold-induced syndromes pain (White, 2007; Wang and Wang, 2005), anti-clotting, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, and analgesic activities (Chrubasik et al., 2005; Ali et al., 2008). Used as food spice (Daudu et al., 2012; Eric et al., 2011). It is used as a remedy for a plethora of ailments including arthritis, digestive maladies, cardiovascular complaints and respiratory illness (Remadevi et al., 2005; Williamson, 2002), nausea, headache, fever, cold (Rasmussen, 2011), digestive and cardiovascular disorders and diabetes (Butt and Sultan, 2011). The essential oil of ginger is used for muscle and joint pain, sprains, colds, nausea, diarrhea, alcoholism, and helping the healing of broken bones (Worwood, 1990). It is used in fresh form, sliced preserved in syrup or candy, paste, dried form, or flavoring tea (Altman and Marcussen, 2001). It is used for the treatment of nausea, respiratory disorders, cardiovascular health, and rheumatic disorders (Polasa and Nirmala, 2003), painful menstrual periods, common cold, flu-like symptoms (Liang, 1992). It also has immunomodulatory properties and is reported to inhibit various inflammatory mediators such as prostaglandins and pro-inflammatory cytokines (Grzanna et al., 2005; Sharma et al., 1994), osteoarthritis (Shen et al., 2003). However, *Z. officinale* is traditionally used for several gastrointestinal disorders including diarrhea (Nadkarni, 1976). Since the use of *Z. officinale* has been associated with only a few insignificant side effects and with no known drug or herb interactions, it has been considered as a safe herbal medicine (Ali et al., 2008). Inspired by the health benefits of *Z. officinale*, the Chinese and the Americans have included it in their official pharmacopeias (Ernst and Pittler, 2000). Oral ingestion of ginger extract has been shown to have hypocholesterolemic, hypolipidemic, and antiatherosclerotic effects in cholesterol-fed rabbits (Bhandari et al., 1998) and rats (Fuhrman et al., 2000). It is used for curing rheumatism, arthritis, and muscular problem (Grant and Lutz, 2000). Inhibition of LDL oxidation and attenuated development of atherosclerosis has also been observed in apolipoprotein E-deficient mice (Thomson et al., 2002). Africans and West Indians also use ginger medicinally and the Greeks and Romans use it as spice (Tyler et al., 1981). The Chinese take ginger for a wide variety of medical problems such as stomachache, diarrhea, nausea, cholera, asthma, heart conditions, respiratory disorders, toothache and rheumatic complaints (Wagner and Hikino, 1965). In Ayurveda, ginger has been recommended for use as a carminative, diaphoretic, antispasmodic, expectorant, peripheral circulatory stimulant, astringent, appetite stimulant, anti-inflammatory agent, diuretic, and digestive aid (Warrier, 1989). In the United States, ginger is recommended to relieve and prevent nausea caused by motion sickness and morning sickness (Rockville, 1998; Mowrey and Clayson, 1982). Ben-Arye (2006) investigated that ginger can be used in the treatment of hyperemesis gravidarum. Ginger is effective in the treatment of cough and cold (Grøntved et al., 1988; Gao and Zhang, 2010). Gingerols present in ginger have analgesic, sedative, antipyretic, antibacterial, and gastrointestinal tract motility effects (Azu et al., 2006). Ginger and its effective components exhibit potent antioxidant (Lee et al., 1986; Kubra & Jaganmohanrao, 2012; Jeena et al., 2013; Semwal et al., 2015), anti-inflammatory (Penna et al., 2003; Kubra & Jaganmohanrao, 2012; Jeena et al., 2013; Semwal et al., 2015; de Lima et al., 2018), anti-lipid (Kadnur et al., 2005), anti-diabetic (Islam and Choi, 2008; Kato et al., 2006) and anti-tumor activities (Kim et al., 2008; de Lima et al., 2018). Mao et al., (2019) stated that ginger is useful in curing various problems like cardiovascular, and can be used also as antioxidant, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antiemetic, anticancer, neuroprotective, respiratory protective, antiobesity, and anti-nausea activities.

Pests and Diseases: The ginger crop is susceptible to a range of diseases that can dramatically reduce yields, of which the most serious is soft rot or rhizome rot (Purseglove et al., 1981). The virulent *Pythium* spp. infection

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leads to significant losses, both in the field and storage with severe attacks resulting in total crop loss. In mature plants, the stems yellow become and collapse while the rhizome becomes soft, putrid, and evil-smelling. Prevention includes soil solarisation, mulching with neem leaves, and the selection of disease-free rhizomes for planting (Dohroo, 2005). Other fungal diseases include yellows (caused by *Fusarium* spp.) and *Phyllosticta* leaf spot (Purseglove et al., 1981; Dohroo, 2005) whilst the most significant bacterial disease is a wilt caused by *Pseudomonas solanacearum*, a plant pathogen with a wide host range (Kamar and Haywood, 2005). The most serious ginger pest is the shoot borer, *Conogethes punctiferalis* (synonym: *Dichocrocis punctiferalis*) which is prevalent in India, Asia, Africa, North and South America, and Australia. Pesticides, biological controls, and cultivation practices are used to limit the damage caused by this pest (Devasabaryam and Koya, 2005).

Cultivation: It is a tropical plant, a warm, humid climate with rainfall of 3000 -4000mm is generally required (Uptala et al., 2006). In the Southern area, it is grown in April/May for a December harvest while in the Northern area, irrigation is necessary (Nybe and Raj, 2005). It can be grown in a wide range of soils but well-drained, aerated, sandy, or clay loam is preferable (Utpala et al., 2006) with a pH of 5 -7; growth is significantly reduced at a pH of 8 or above (Xizhen, 2005). The crop is propagated vegetatively with small pieces of rhizome, each with at least one viable bud, chosen for planting. Fertilizers are required, usually in the form of animal manures. The crop is mulched with green leaves for weed control and to reduce evaporation with banana leaves giving the best results (Nybe and Raj, 2005).

Constituents: Shirin and Prakash (2010) reported tannins, flavonoids, phenols, carotenoids, protein, fat, ash, moisture, soluble fibers, insoluble fibers, vitamin C, carbohydrates, Zn, Cr, P, Ca, Fe, Cu, Mn. α -pinene, zinziberenol, linalool, terpineol, borneol, eucalyptol, 1, 8-cineole, cubenol, cadinol, β -eudesmol, nerolidol (Toure and Xiaoming, 2007), farnesene, bisabolene, zingiberene, α -curcumene, sesquiphellandrene (Lawrence, 2000), vitamin A, phytosterols, nicotinic acid, amino acids (Langner et al., 1998; Shukla and Singh, 2007), diarylheptanoids, 8-gingerdiol, 10-gingerdiol, 6- gingerdione, 10-gingerdione, 6-paradol, 4- gingerdiol, 6-gingerdiol, 1-dehydrogingerdione (Ali et al., 2008; Govindarajan, 1982), methyl 4-shogaol, 6-isoshogaol, methyl 8-paradol, 1,7-bis-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxyphenyl)-5-methoxyheptan-3-one, methyl diacetoxy-[8]-gingerdiol, methyl 6-isogingerol, 5-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxyphenyl)-pent-2-en-1-al, 3-acetoxydihydro-[6]-paradol methyl ether, 1-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxyphenyl)-2-nonadecen-1-one, 6-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxyphenyl)-2-nonyl-2- hydroxytetrahydropyran, 1-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-2,4-dehydro-6-decanone, 5-acetoxy-3-deoxy-[6]-gingerol, 1,7-bis-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxyphenyl)-3-hydroxy-5-acetoxyheptane, 5-(4'-hydroxy-3'-methoxyphenyl)-3-hydroxy-1-pentanal, acetoxy-3-dihydrodemethoxy-6-shogaol, (Jolad et al., 2005), α -cedrene, decanal, γ -elemene, cubebene, α -citral, murolan-3, 9 (11)-diene-10-peroxy, eudesm-4, β -bisabolol (Zhao et al., 2015), hexanal, octanal, isocaryophyllen, 1-hexadecanol, 1-hexadecene, thujyl alcohol, β - elemene, careen, decanal, isobornyl acetate, propiconazole, 2-undecanone, (Z) Beta-farnesene, elemol, nerolidol Z, dehydrolinalool, d-nerolidol, trans-carveol, epi-bicyclo sesquihallendrene β -myrcene (Purnomo et al.,2010), 1,8-cineole, trans-dimethoxy citral, trans-linalool oxide, trans-linalool oxide acetate, α -terpineol, geraniol, (Z)-dimethoxycitral, (E)-dimethoxy citral, (Gupta et al., 2011), saponin, oxalate, cyanogenic glycoside (Nwinuka et al., 2005), glycol monopalmitate, isovanillin, maleimide-5-oxime, hexacosanoic acid 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester, p-hydroxy benzaldehyde, adenine, 1-(omega-ferulyloxygeratyl) glycerols (Bao et al., 2010), z-citral, ocimene (Raina et al., 2005), e-citral, camphene (Raina et al., 2005; Purnomo et al.,2010), neral (Gupta et al., 2011; Ekundayo et al., 1988; Wohlmuth et al., 2006), geranial (Gupta et al., 2011, Ekundayo et al., 1988; Wohlmuth et al., 2006; Sasidharan et al., 2012; Yu et al., 2007), 1,8-cineole (Ekundayo et al., 1988; Sultan et al., 2005), citral (Wohlmuth et al., 2006; Sultan et al., 2005; Purnomo et al., 2010), flavonoids (Qin et al., 2008; Hou et al., 2007; Mo et al., 2005; Idris et al., 2019), 10-gingerol and 12-gingerol (Park et al., 2008), oleoresin (Onwuka et al., 2002; Ebewele and Jimoh, 1988). 8-gingerol, 6-gingerol, 10-gingerol, paradols, shogaols, gingerones (Zhang et al., 2017), R-terpineol, camphene, zingiberene, p-cineole and pentadecanoic

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acid (El-Ghorab et al., 2010), 6, 8 and 10-gingerols (Wohlmuth et al., 2005), quercetin and total phenols (Idris et al., 2019).

PHARMACOLOGY

Analgesic activity: The analgesic activity of the *Z. officinale* oil was evaluated by the acetic acid-induced writhing in mice and hot-plate test in mice. The study reported the significant analgesic effect against chemically and thermally-induced nociceptive pain stimuli in mice (Yong-liang et al., 2011). The rhizome extract (50 and 100 mg/kg body weight) significantly reduced the number of writhing induced by acetic acid in mice (Raji et al., 2002; Young et al., 2005; Jeena et al., 2013).

Antioxidant activity: Kruawan and Kangsadalampai (2006) envisaged the antioxidant activity of the aqueous extract and stated that it has high antioxidant activity. El-Ghorab et al. (2010) also reported this activity of the ginger extracts. Liu et al., (2008) stated ethanol extract of this plant has antioxidant activity and its FRAP value 0.806 mmol of Fe(II)/g dry weight. Min et al., (2017) investigated that both organic fertilizer with mycorrhiza and tissue culture together increased the constituents and antioxidant effects of *Z. officinale*.

Immunosuppressant drug: Chiang et al., (2006) investigated that ginger significantly decreased the oral bioavailability of cyclosporine, and the interaction should occur at the absorption phase. Patients treated with cyclosporine should be discouraged from using ginger products to ensure the efficacy of cyclosporine.

Effects on the cardiovascular system: In traditional Chinese medicine, ginger is used to improve the flow of body fluids. It stimulates blood circulation throughout the body by a powerful stimulatory effect on the heart muscle and by dilating blood vessels (Shoji et al., 1982). The improved circulation is believed to increase the cellular metabolic activity, thus contributing to the relief of cramps and tension (Kobayashi et al., 1988). A Japanese study showed that active constituents in ginger reduced the blood pressure and decreased cardiac workload (Tanabe et al., 1993). It reduced the formation of pro-inflammatory prostaglandins and thromboxane thus lowering the clotting ability of the blood (Bordia et al., 1997). The inhibition of platelet aggregation by ginger is more than the similar effects observed with garlic and onion (Srivastava, 1984 a,b; Srivastava, 1986). Furthermore, it can prevent the increase in cholesterol levels following the intake of a cholesterol-rich diet (Gujral et al., 1978). Ansari et al., (2006) reported that ethanolic extract pretreatment enhances the antioxidant defense against ISO-induced oxidative myocardial injury in rats and exhibit cardioprotective property.

Antidiabetic activity: It promotes glucose clearances in insulin-responsive peripheral tissues, which is crucial in maintaining blood glucose homeostasis. Evidence from in vitro studies has demonstrated that extract and its pungent gingerol principles enhanced glucose uptake in cultured L6 rat skeletal muscle cells and 3T3-L1 adipocytes (Noipha et al., 2010; Li et al., 2012; Sekiya et al., 2004). Acute hyperglycemia evokes gastric slow-wave dysrhythmias via endogenous prostaglandin generation and ginger exhibits slow-wave antiarrhythmic effects (Gonlachanvit et al., 2003). El-Rokh et al., 2010 evaluated the antihypercholesterolaemic effects of aqueous extract in hypercholesterolaemic rat models and tested for lipid profile [serum total cholesterol (TC), HDL-cholesterol (HDL-C), LDL-C and triglyceride levels] was measured at zero time and 2 and 4 weeks after ginger and atorvastatin treatment. They came to know that the infusion in the three doses used after 2 and 4 weeks of treatment induces a significant decrease in all lipid profile parameters which were measured and improved the risk ratio

Antimicrobial activity: Studies of El-Baroty et al., (2012); Onyeagba et al., (2004); Adeshina et al., (2011); Sebiomo et al., (2011); Fawzi et al., (2009); Bansod and Rai (2008) showed that oil had significant inhibitory activity against strains of bacteria (*Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. pyogenes*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Serratia marcescens* and pathogenic fungi (*Aspergillus niger*, *Penicillium notatum*, *Mucora heimalis*, *Alternaria alternaria*, *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*). Similarly, da Silva et al., (2012) reported that essential oil possessed antifungal activity against *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus*. Betoni et al., (2006) worked on the antimicrobial activity of different medicinal plants including ginger and they reported that ginger showed limited synergistic capacity against

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Staphylococcus aureus in vitro condition. Islam et al., (2014) reported that soybean oil extract of ginger at boiling temperature has potential antimicrobial activity and could be used in food preparation to get the synergistic effect of soybean and ginger. Ginger has direct anti-microbial activity and thus can be used in the treatment of bacterial infections (Tan and Vanitha, 2004; Weil, 2005; Gull et al., 2012). Ginger flavonoids have antimicrobial activity (Yu et al., 2009; Wang, Chu, 2009; Akoachere et al., 2002). It eliminates harmful bacteria from the digestive tract which are responsible for diarrhea especially in children (Wood, 1988).

Anticancer activity: Many workers had reported that ginger possessed anticancer activity using mice or cancer cells line for examples Park et al., (2006) reported antipancreatic cancer cell, Lv et al., (2012) human lung and colon cancer cells and also in mice, Yoshimi et al., (1992) gastrointestinal tract, Murakami et al., (2004); Bode (2003); Manju and Nalini (2005) colon, Nagasawa et al., (2002) breast, Wu et al., (2010) 12-O-tetradecanoylphorbol 13-acetate (TPA)-induced tumor promotion in mice. Kim et al., (2005) 6-gingerol inhibited the proliferation and tube formation of primary cultured human endothelial cells in response to vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), caused cell cycle arrest in the G1 phase, and suppressed experimental metastases in tumor-bearing mice. Ju et al., (2012) administration of 6-gingerol greatly enhanced the number of tumor-infiltrating lymphocytes in murine tumors. 6-gingerol acts against breast cancer (Lee et al., 2008); skin cancer (Kim et al., 2004; Kim et al., 2005; Nigam et al., 2010); ovarian cancer (Rhode et al., 2007). Tahir et al., (2015) investigated that the combination of ginger and Gelam honey has a chemopreventive effect and induces the death of colon cancer. Park et al., (2014) investigated that ginger play a crucial role in the reduction of cell viability and apoptosis by GL may be a result of ATF3 promoter activation and subsequent increase of ATF3 expression through ERK1/2 activation in human colorectal cancer cells

Effects on the gastrointestinal tract: The effectiveness of ginger in motion sickness was higher as compared to that of dimenhydrinate. Because of digestion, absorption, relieve constipation and flatulence by increasing muscular activity in the digestive tract (Stewart et al., 1991; Mowrey and Clayson, 1982). Ginger administration before elective gynecologic laparoscopy was also found to be effective in preventing postoperative nausea and vomiting (Yamahara and Huang, 1990; Ernst and Pittler, 2000; Al-Yahya et al., 1989).

Anthelmintic activity: Aqueous extracts of rhizome possess significant anthelmintic activity against the earthworm *Pheretima posthuma* (Dubey et al., 2010) while methanol extracts killed all the test worms (*Haemonchus contortus*) within two hours post-exposure being 100% effective (Iqbal et al., 2001).

Antiviral activity: Sookkongwaree et al., (2006) worked on the antiviral effect of ginger for inhibition of proteases from human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1), hepatitis C virus (HCV), and human cytomegalovirus (HCMV). HCV protease was most efficiently inhibited by the extracts from *Zingiber officinale*, with little difference between the aqueous and the methanol extracts.

Larvicidal activity: Lin et al., (2010) envisage the larvicidal activity of *Z. officinale* against *Angiostrongylus cantonensis*. First, they isolate [6]-gingerol, [10]-shogaol, [10]-gingerol, [6]-shogaol and hexahydrocurcumin from the roots and then screened for larvicidal activity against the larvae of *A. cantonensis*. Among the isolates, [10]-gingerol showed higher larvicidal than hexa-hydrocurcumin, mebendazole, and albendazole.

Antiallergic activity: Tewtrakul and Subhadhirasakul (2007) reported that ethanolic and water extracts, together with volatile oils from the rhizomes of six selected Zingiberaceous plants, including *Zingiber officinale* investigated for their anti-allergic activities using a RBL-2H3 cell line and their result indicated that *Z. officinale* has no positive results to use for the treatment of allergy and allergic-related diseases.

Side effects: In general, ginger appears to be safe. Its side effects were not reported in most studies (Kobayashi et al., 2004; Borrelli et al., 2005; Oliveira et al., 2005). A study of healthy subjects reports no severe side effects, based on biochemistry data (Oliveira et al., 2005). While studies of treating nausea and vomiting or of cancer patients reported ginger side effects and the side effects are gastrointestinal disturbance, sleepiness, restless, sedation, and heartburn (Manusirivithaya et al., 2004; Sripramote and Lekhyananda, 2003; Betz et al., 2005), nausea and vomiting (Haniadka et al., 2012; Palatty et al., 2013). While Marx et al., (2017) have reported that ginger has been recommended for the treatment of nausea and vomiting during cancer. Finally, ginger may interact with surgical medications including anesthesia, leading to arrhythmias, poor wound healing, bleeding,

photosensitivity reaction, and prolonged sedation (Ciocon et al., 2004). Ginger may also interact with certain anticoagulants and analgesics to cause bleeding (Kruth et al., 2004).

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